

Speculation on Information, Scaling and the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis Distributions

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 9, 2026

We suggest that if one wishes to use a probabilistic description of a gas of independent particles, then one may write: $E_{ave} = \frac{\int c_1 \sqrt{e} de e p(e/T)}{\int c_1 \sqrt{e} de e p(e/T)}$ where $p(e/T)$ is not normalized. e/T is used, with T , an unknown parameter, because probability has no units. If one makes the assumption that e ranges from 0 to infinite, then $E = T * \text{Number}$. Thus, T is a parameter proportional to E_{ave} and also E_{total} . One may then ask whether there exists a math function $S(T, e_i, p_1(e_i/T))$ (p_1 is normalized) which describes the system in the following sense. If $T \rightarrow T + dT$ and $p_1(e_i/T) - p_1(e_i/T) + dp_1(e_i/T)$, can $dS/dT dT$ describe the changes in the physical constraints $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i p_1(e_i/T) C(T)$ where $C(T)$ is the normalization of $p(e_i/T)$ and $\sum_i p_1(e_i/T) = 1$? We suggest that if scaling is considered, one may only have $S(e_i/T, p(e_i/T))$ as a change in the scale used to measure e_i and T should not change the statistical function. If this is the case, $g(p(e_i/T)) = -e_i/T$, where g is $-1 * \text{the inverse of } p_1$. As a result, one may seek $F(g(p(e_i/T)), p(e_i/T))$ which is strictly a function of $p(e_i/T)$ and may be able to describe the two constraints upon a change in T . One way to have this occur is for $F = \sum_i p_1(e_i/T) g(p_1)$ such that: $g(p_1) = -e_i/T$ and $p_1 dg/dp_1 = 1$, where p_1 is the normalized probability. This leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. If one assumes a physical constraint of $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ power q and $F = \sum_i p(e_i/T)$ power q $g(p)$, then this leads to the Tsallis distribution.

We have discussed some of these ideas in previous notes, but the main point we present here is that scaling, i.e. the form e_i/T in F means that F is strictly a function of $p(e_i/T)$. One does not have to start with the assumption of an a priori function $F(p(e_i/T))$ as we did in previous notes. Furthermore, $p(e_i/T)$ contains both e_i and global E_{ave} information and so it is quite plausible that a statistical function of $p(e_i/T)$ could describe the constraints in the problem.

We also consider the question of energy conservation in individual scattering collisions.

Notion of a Probability and the Temperature Parameter

One may try to consider a gas of N particles in a statistical manner. This would suggest a probability(e_i). Given that probability is dimensionless one would expect $p(e_i/T)$, even if p is unnormalized. If one wishes to make the further assumption that $p(e_i)$'s are independent, even though there is a fixed total energy E , one would need to make the assumption that e ranges from 0 to infinity. This means that the $p(e_i/T)$ must be a rapidly falling function of e_i so that the average value is $E_{ave} = E/N$. If one makes this assumption, one may write;

$$E_{ave} = \frac{\int c_1 \sqrt{e} de e p(e/T)}{\int c_1 \sqrt{e} de e p(e/T)} \quad ((1))$$

For e ranging from 0 to infinite: $E = T * \text{Number} \quad ((2))$

Thus, T in $p(e_i/T)$ is proportional to E_{ave} and E and so p carries both local and global energy information.

Consideration of a Statistical Function

We postulate that existence of a statistical function:

$$F(e_i, T, p_1(e_i/T)) \quad ((3))$$

which describes the gas. If this is the case, a change in $T \rightarrow T+dT$ should reveal the two constraints present:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p_1(e_i/T) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p_1(e_i/T) = E_{ave} \quad ((4))$$

We next suggest that ((3)) should be invariant to a change in the scale used to measure energy. This means that one must have e_i/T as the variable, i.e.

$$F(e_i/T, p_1(e_i/T)) \quad ((4))$$

One may, however, define:

$$g(p_1(e_i/T)) = -e_i/T \quad ((5)) \quad (\text{i.e. } -1 \text{ times the inverse of } p_1)$$

$$\text{Then: } F(g(p_1), p_1) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is a function of p_1 alone. Next, one may change $T \rightarrow T+dT$ to see if the two physical constraints emerge.

$$\text{One may write: } F = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } p_1(e_i/T) g(p_1(e_i/T)) \quad ((6))$$

to mimic the energy constraint. (We have done this in previous notes.) Whatever remains must create the constraint $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p_1(e_i/T) = 1$. This means that:

$$p_1 dg/dp_1 = 1 \quad ((7))$$

(One might use a constant other than 1, but that does not really matter as one sees that $g = \ln(p_1)$ and a constant b instead of 1 leads to $g = \ln(p_1^b) = b \ln(p_1)$ and so \ln is the essential function.

$\ln(p_1)$ and ((5)) then yield the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

Tsallis Case

To describe the Tsallis case, one may change the energy constraint in ((4)) to

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p_1(e_i/T)^q = E_{ave} \quad ((8))$$

while leaving $\sum_i p_1(e_i/T) = 1$ unchanged. Then:

$$p_1 \text{ power } q \text{ dg/dp}_1 = 1 \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{This leads to: } g = (1 - p_1 \text{ power } (1-q)) / (1-q) \quad ((10))$$

If one wishes g to become \ln for $q=1$, which causes ((8)) to become the MB constraint.

Conservation of Energy

We assumed independent $p_1(e_i/T)$'s in the first section. This means that there must be elastic scattering occurring in order for energy to be conserved, it seems. The solution $p_1(e_i/T) = C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$ yields

$$p_1(e_i)p_1(e_j) = p_1(e_k)p_1(e_l) \text{ if } e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l. \quad ((11))$$

An alternative way of solving for the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distribution should be:

$$\text{MB case: } F = \sum_i p_1(e_i/T) g(p_1(e_i/T))$$

If $g(p_1(e_i/T)) = -e_i/T$ as assumed above, then:

$$g(p_1(e_i/T)) + g(p_1(e_j/T)) = -1/T (e_i+e_j) = -1/T (\ln(p_1(e_i/T)) + \ln(p_1(e_j/T))) \quad ((12))$$

suggesting that $g = \ln$.

In principle, one does not formally have to compute: $p \text{ d}g/\text{d}p = 1$ as done above, but this must hold nevertheless. These ideas apply to the Maxwell-Boltzmann case.

In the Tsallis case, one has the parameter q and so ((11)) does not apply.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one wishes to describe a gas of independent particles by $p(e_i)$, one should use $p(e_i/T)$ where T has energy units and is unknown. Here p is unnormalized. To really have independent particles, one should allow e_i to range from 0 to infinite leading to the Eave definition ((1)) and $E_{ave} = T * \text{Number}$. Thus, T in e_i/T is proportional to the total energy (and average energy). One might wish to describe the gas by a single function $F(e_i, T, p_1(e_i/T))$, where p_1 is normalized. If the energy scale changes, the function should remain unchanged and so we propose $F(e_i/T, p_1(e_i/T))$, but one may introduce $g(p_1(e_i/T)) = -e_i/T$ i.e. g is -1 times the inverse function of p_1 . The catch is that changes in F when $T \rightarrow T+dT$ must describe changes in the two constraints: $E_{ave} = \text{number} * T$ and $\sum_i p_1(e_i/T) = 1$. For this to be the case, we suggest $F = \sum_i p_1(e_i/T) g(p_1(e_i/T))$ such that: $g(p_1(e_i/T)) = -e_i/T$ and $p_1 \text{ dg/dp}_1 = 1$. This

yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. For the Tsallis distribution, we use the energy constraint $\sum_i e_i p^q(e_i/T)$ power q .